

THE BHAVAS / HOUSES AND PLANETS SIGNIFYING WEALTH, HEALTH AND VEHICLE / CONVEYANCE

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Abstract:

The very essential and important feature and the goal to achieve in the life by everyone is to get the Yoga of having Wealth, Health and Vehicle etc. Here we will do the research on the possible rules which provide these Yogas through the bhavas and planets of our birth horoscope.

Key Words: Ascendant, Ascendant Lord, 4th House and 4th House Lord, The Planets the Moon, Venus and Mars.

Introduction:

It is very much important to lead a happy life of a man is to have an abode. Next essential is to have a Vehicle and the pleasure of journey. In the birth chart the strength of the following and the combinations between them, are to be considered for the prediction – the Ascendant lord, the 4th lord, the planets the Moon, Venus and Mars. One cannot delineate correctly unless one is thoroughly acquainted with all rules and cannons of astrology. The delineations of Vehicle, wealth are to be seen from the ascendant and the 4th house. In the horoscope of a native the Ascending signs indicating physical appearance, personality, character. So the qualities as shown by the ascendant will stamp on the individuals and denotes personality. Personality may be considered as the general expressions which characterize the person that which distinguishes him from others and identifies him. If the ascendant and the ascendant lord are natural benefic and functional benefic and their aspect, and aspect of the ascendant lord on the ascendant make the individual to be happy, healthy and enjoy the life with all comforts. The specialty of the native seen only through the ascendant. The ascendant takes the control of all other houses and direct it. If the strength of the ascendant is less than the other houses, the native will not be able to enjoy the full effects of the other houses. Now, we will see the significations of ascendant from the ancient publications. This house signifies life, longevity, happiness, health, nature, fame, respect, honor, complexion, status, vitality, courage, determination, political interest, peace of mind, appearance, capability of earning, disgrace, ego, diseases, natural habits, managing others wealth, looks after animals sorrows or sufferings. It also shows general strength and weakness. These all are mentioned in "Uthira Kalamirutham". In manthreswara's "Bala Deepika" it is shortly mentioned that Lagna (Asc) bhava signifies Body, rise, appearance, birth etc. Generally 1st house represents health, mind, appearance, activeness, laziness. The Karaka for the 1st house is the Sun. Now we will see the significations of 4th house mentioned in the "Uthrakalamirutha": - Mother, education, health, Property and the Karak for this is the Moon. The Government, house, travel, vehicle, vehicle yoga, oil bath, relatives, friends, cloth, and well. Yoga of water, happiness, milk, good name, the medicine makes miracle in curing diseases, tent, paviliyan, success, blame, fatigue, ponds, land, garden, park, mother side relatives, sagacity, entrance, conclusion, losing place and job, inheritance, amruth, CID work, anthill, Veda, knowledge about myth, ox, cow, horse, wet land, more growth of paddy.

In "bala Deepika" the following significations are given:- house, land, maternal uncle, sister's son, relatives, friends, vehicle, good position in the Government, cow, ox, scents, jewelers, dresses, happiness, water, land, bridge etc. In "Jothisha prangyana Deepika" it is mentioned that the art of learning, mother, business, house, success and improvement, healthy, sexual union of newly married couple, true wisdom, milk, cow, a scared shrine etc. Generally, 4th house indicates mother, education, vehicle, wealth, health etc. A native to enjoy the above said effects of a bhava, the 9th house should support and that should be seen for the better results. The signification of 9th house is Jupiter. Charitable, religious, justice and love for all, good natured, religious journeys, penance, respecting elders, medicine, discipline, praying God, taking interest to learn more, vehicle, virtuous, sincere, dutiful, honest, wealthy, wisdom, moral aims, unusual matters, pilgrimage, respect, moral stories, long journeys, holy bath in rivers, religious group singing, happy, paternal wealth, progeny, daughter, different types of properties, horses, elephants, buffalo, durbar, Brahmin culture, belief, materials dropped (sticks of different trees = Avis) in the Homa, money flow all these are mentioned in "uthira kalamirutha". In "Bala Deepika" the significations are – preceptor, Guru, teacher, father, god, paternal elders (pitr), auspicious functions, religious merit of last birth, and worship of God (pooja), penance, religious activities and the respect achieved through that, grand – son, all these can be found out from 9th house. In "Jothisha prangyana Deepika" it is mentioned that the 9th house signifies father, paternal property, charity, fortunateness (bhagya), chaultry, friary, growth, improvement, school, temple, temple renovation, preaching of Vedas or mantras. Supernatural powers obtained by dev, pond, lake, living in mountain and forest, enshrine etc. Generally 9th house indicates, good deeds, donate, devotion, pilgrimage, lucky etc.

Planets Signifying Wealth, Health and Vehicle / Conveyance:

The concerned planets are the Moon, Mars and Venus. So, let us see the significations of these planets.

Significations of the Moon:

The Moon is the dependant of the Sun. It receives the light rays of the Sun and glow. The lord of the night is the Moon. Athma Karak is the Sun. The body is the essential place for the existence of soul. Without the mother there is no generation of new born. So, the Moon is the karak for mother. The athma karak is the Sun; the karak for mind is the Moon. For wisdom the need of the Moon is very much important. From the normal thinking to attain supernatural thinking. So, the Moon rules the mind. The Moon is mother, queens, umbrella, women, liquid, water sources, sea travel, shipping, fisherman, port, seaman, travelers, bath-room, business man, food, milk business. Buildings adjacent to water sources, general stores, liquor business, rice, salt, slattern, chaultry, washer man, flower with fragrance, brass, butter, pearl, pearl ornaments, delicious meal, cloth, horse, Maa Parasakthi, fame, strength all these things are signified by the Moon. Affliction of the Moon is to be studied very closely. This will denote as a general poor success with subordinates, servants and employees. So one should serve others. Afflicted nervous system and general health. As for as our body concerned the body, stomach, digestion, urinary organs, uterus diseases in respect of women, bottom portion of brain, severe diseases, eye problems, coldness is etc. represented by the Moon.

As per the mind concerned the consciousness, cognition, feelings, speed, home sick, imagination, the things possible in the normal life, disturbed mind, religious thoughts, fearless, inferiority complex, frugality, grasping ability, precaution etc. The moon is responsible for the subtlety body. It is said that after death our ancestors reach Chandra lok and live there with their subtlety body. That is why we do "tharpan" on that day when the sun and the Moon are together i.e. Amavasya. The "Thithi" is a very important in astrology and in Panchank. When the Moon move apart from the Sun that is considered as "Thithi". After new Moon day (Amavasya) the Moon is called as waning Moon and after the full Moon day it is called as Waxing Moon. Moreover, all the auspicious functions, temple ceremonies, elder's memorable days (sarththa thithi) are celebrated considering the position of the Moon. For example, Atchya Thiruthiya, Ganesh Chaturthi, Rishi Panchami, Nag Panchami, Rath Saptami, JanmaShtami, Sri Ram Navami, Vijaya Dasami, Vaikund Ekadasi, Chitra Pournami etc.

The characteristics of Mars:- There is much connections with Mars and human life. There is no man without anger, beastliness and brutality, the main character of the Mars. The lord of beastliness in the low level and the lord of arrogance, ego, and pride in the higher level it is Mars. The beastliness is due to the speed, urge and strength of our feelings. At that time there is no value for intelligence. In the case of ego, there is no value for wisdom. Due to that we are unable to reach the infinite wisdom. In the boundary of this two position men happen to travel throughout his life. Both these characters are due to the desire and selfishness. Though both are essential for our life, when we act with more of these feelings it becomes meaningless. When we are unable to achieve our desire, the anger and frenzy come out from our mind. So, when we control the character of Mars our courage, self-confidence, bravery, achievement, strength, freedom, ability to do the work, interest to have the improvement in our life, leadership quality, magnanimity, dignity all are increasing. In the world level Mars signifies the following:- Military soldiers, captain, general of armed forces, sports persons, wrestlers, doctors, engineer, weapons, fire, jobs concerned with fire, butcher, mortuary, barber, copper, red gram dal, coral, theft, accidents etc.

In our body it signifies the following:- head, nose, smelling ability, fever, wounds, swellings, small pox, burnetc. In the real life mars signifies land, brother, lord Subramaniya, trees full of flowers, virility, enthusiasm and sudden death etc. The planet Venus signifies the following:- the feeling of pleasantry (elegant) and taste add together to form a peaceful atmosphere. These feelings are brought out through our thoughts, decisions, words, activity and body. Venus represents beauty, wife and conjugal life, fame and titles, glory and sensual enjoyments, female and sexual enjoyment during day time, erotic's and female worship, company of prostitutes, Epicureanism, self gratification and lust, music, dancing and drama (triple symphony), sandal, flower and aromatics, musk, civet, cots, beddings, curtains all such paraphernalia, company of princess and bodily enjoyments, youth, sensuality, lustrous, beautiful and amorous eyes, wealth and splendor, equipages and cars, garlands, flowers and bouquets, flags, honours, flashy style and princely living, law, literature, poetry and dramatic works. Diamonds, rubies and silver vessels, sea trade, navy, marine occupations, exotic products, foreign ideas and fashions optimism and survival of the fittest, sri vidhya uppasana, desire to rule over mankind, friendship, mammon (riches), deductions and experimentalism, charming speech, minister, marriage and other auspicious celebrations, virility, south east, peacock, parrot, paksha (15 days), Brahmin, passionate (rajoguna), vasantha ritu (chitra, vaishaka), taste, mrks on face, silk, yajurveda, excellent cloths, pearls, soury taste, mineral, lakshmi, cow gram, cow, milk, card, swan, music organs, home, vehicle, beans, etc.

Planets and house set up:

Wealth = The Moon + Mars, The Moon and Mars combination and mutual transfer

The Moon is in the star of Mars or vice versa. The strong Moon and Mars. Aspect and combination of natural benefic and in the houses 1, 5, 9. The combination of Lagna lord and the 4th lord confer wealth.

The Moon and Mars combine and in the position of 6, 8, 12th houses will obstruct procurement of wealth. Same thing happens when The Moon and Venus are in 6/8/12 from cancer sign. The same rules are applicable to the 4th house in the birth horoscope also. In the case of vehicle the lagna and lagna lord, the planets the Moon, Venus and the 4th house are to be taken as granted. The combination of lagna and the 4th lord. The connection between lagna lord and 4th house or 4th lord.

Venus + the Moon combination are taken as a rule

In concern with the lagna:

If Aries is the lagna and the 4th house is Cancer. The lagna lord Mars and the 4th lord is the Moon. Above said rules and this strong combination confer vehicle, wealth and conveyance facilities. If Taurus is the lagna and the 4th house is Leo. The lagna lord is Venus and the 4th lord is the Sun. Above said rules and this strong combination confer vehicle, wealth and conveyance facilities. If Gemini is the lagna and the 4th house is Virgo. The lagna lord and the 4th lord is the Mercury. Above said rules and strong Mercury, and combination of benefic planets, and the lagna yoga karaka + Mercury in 1, 5, 9th houses confer vehicle, wealth and conveyance facilities. If Cancer is the lagna and the 4th house is Libra. The lagna lord Moon and the 4th lord is the Venus. Above said rules and this strong combination confer vehicle, wealth and conveyance facilities. If Leo is the lagna and the 4th house is Scorpio. The lagna lord the Sun and the 4th lord is the Mars. Above said rules and this strong combination confer vehicle, wealth and conveyance facilities. If Virgo is the lagna and the 4th house is Sagittarius. The lagna lord Mercury and the 4th lord is Jupiter. Above said rules and this strong combination and the connection of (trikona) lord of decanate, confer vehicle, wealth and conveyance facilities. If Libra is the lagna and the 4th house is Capricorn. The lagna lord Venus and the 4th lord is Saturn. Above said rules and this strong combination the connection of lagna benefic confer vehicle, wealth and conveyance facilities.

If Scorpio is the lagna and the 4th house is Aquarius. The lagna lord is Mars and the 4th lord is Saturn. Above said rules and strong combination confer the native, vehicle, wealth and conveyance facilities. If Sagittarius is the lagna and the 4th house is Pisces. The lagna lord and the 4th lord is Jupiter. Jupiter is a natural benefic. Above said rules and strong combination and the connection of (trikona) lord of decanate, confer the native, vehicle, wealth and conveyance facilities. Moreover, the connection of the strong Mars, the Moon, strong Venus and the Moon connection makes this yoga. If Capricorn is the lagna and the 4th house is Aries. The lagna lord is Saturn and the 4th lord is Mars. Above said rules and strong combination confer the native, vehicle, wealth and conveyance facilities. If Aquarius is the lagna and the 4th house is Taurus. The lagna lord is Saturn and the 4th lord is Venus. Above said rules and strong combination of Saturn and Venus confer the native, house, vehicle, wealth and conveyance facilities. If Pisces is the lagna and the 4th house is the Gemini. The lagna lord is Jupiter and the 4th lord is Mercury. Above said rules and strong combination confer the native, vehicle, wealth and conveyance facilities.

Mo-7°		Ke-26°	Asc			Ve-26° Ju-10° Ma-28°	Sat-14°
	Rasi 067y04m12d			Asc Ra-26° Su-11°	NAVAMSA		Me-25°
			Ju-4°				Ke-26°
	Ra-26°	Su-11° Ve-26° Sat-28°	Ma-16° Me-22°				Mo-4°

MALE -28/10/1955

In the above horoscope

The lagna lord is – Mercury.

4th Bhava is – Virgo, 4th Lord is – Mercury, 9th Bhava is – Aquarius, 9th Lord is - Saturn

The lagna lord and the 4th lord are Mercury; the 4th lord Mercury is very strong as it is in exaltation and in moola trikona sign. In the 4th bhava Mercury and Mars are together and the Moon aspect both. The lord of Bhakya sthana is in porva punya bhava and in exaltation and the Venus with him is in his own sign. The strong combinations confer the native, vehicle, wealth and conveyance facilities.

Conclusion:

In the natal chart the lagna lord and the strong 4th lord combination, with the aspect or connection of 9th lord, the Moon, Venus and Mars is very much important to confer the native vehicle, wealth and conveyance facilities.

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